

Studies in Thiazino quinoxalines and Quinoxalino benzothiazines

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2H, 3H, 4H (1,4) thiazino (2,3-b) quinoxalines have been synthesised by the condensations of various β -mercaptoethylamines with 2:3-dichloro quinoxalines. The latter on interaction with *o*-amino thiophenols furnished quinoxalino benzothiazines.

We reported a multistep synthesis of 2H, 3H, 4H (1,4) thiazino (2,3-b) quinoxaline¹ (I, $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$) which was alternatively obtained from ethylene dibromide and 2-mercapto-3-amino quinoxaline. The latter was obtained from 2-chloro-3-amino quinoxaline which in turn was obtained from 2:3-dichloro quinoxaline. Here we report a simple one step synthesis of I by the condensation of 2:3-dichloro quinoxaline with β -mercapto ethylamine.

2:3:6-Trichloro and 2:3-Dichloro-6-nitro quinoxaline on condensation with β -mercapto ethylamine gave single products, I ($R_1 = Cl$; $R_2 = R_3 = H$) and I ($R_1 = R_3 = H$; $R_2 = NO_2$). This is due to the relatively enhanced reactivities of C_2-Cl and C_3-Cl in the respective quinoxaline derivatives².

Since 2:3-Dichloro quinoxaline is hydrolysed by dilute acid or alkali² methyl and ethyl ester of cysteine hydrochloride were condensed with 2:3-Dichloro quinoxaline in the presence of triethylamine to furnish the corresponding thiazino quinoxalines. The physical data concerning these compounds is tabulated in Table I.

Likewise condensations of 2:3-Dichloro quinoxalines with *o*-amino thiophenols furnished the corresponding quinoxalino benzothiazines II (Table II).

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2. R. D. Haworth and S. Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 777.

EXPERIMENTAL

2*H*, 3*H*, 4*H*, 1 : 4-*Thiazino* (2,3-*b*) *quinoxaline* (I, $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$) : Dry hydrogen sulphide gas was passed through ethyleneimine (1 ml.) in ethanol solution (50 ml.) at 0° for 1 hr. 2 : 3-Dichloroquinoxaline (2 g.) was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 hr. The solid separated was collected as hydrochloride of I. It was dissolved in water and was basified with sodium carbonate solution and I ($R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$) was obtained. In its IR spectrum (KBr pellet) NH absorbed at 3175 cm^{-1} and the $> C = N$ appeared at 1605 cm^{-1} .

3-*Carbomethoxy*-3 : 4-*dihydro*-2*H*-(1 : 4)*thiazino* (2,3-*b*) *quinoxaline* I ($R_1 = R_2 = H$, $R_3 = \text{COOCH}_3$) : 2 : 3-Dichloro quinoxaline (1.99 g., 0.01 mole) and methyl ester of cysteine hydrochloride (1.70 g., 0.01 mole) were taken in benzene and triethylamine (5 ml.) was added to it. The mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 3 hrs. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol.

I ($R_1 = R_2 = H$, $R_3 = \text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$) was prepared in an identical manner. The data regarding these compounds are given in Table I.

2*H*-*Quinoxalino* (2,3-*b*) (1,4) *benzothiazines* II : (Table II) (a) Equivalent amounts of 2 : 3-Dichloro quinoxalines and *o*-aminothiophenols were refluxed in ethanol. The solid separated out after about 30-40 minutes refluxing. After refluxing for an additional hour the reaction mixture was cooled and the separated product was crystallised from acetic acid.

(b) 2 : 3-Dichloro quinoxaline and *o*-aminothiophenols were mixed when heat evolved. The reaction mixtures were heated in an oil bath for about an hour at 120–30°. The products were crystallised from acetic acid (Table II).

TABLE I

Sl. No.	Product formed			m.p. °C	Solvent of crystallisation	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analytical results*		
	R_1	R_2	R_3					Found %	Reqd. %	
1.	H	H	H	225	Ethanol/ether	50	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{ClN}_3\text{S}$	N,	17.52	17.57
				212	Ethanol	50	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{N}_3\text{S}$	C,	59.30	59.11
								N,	20.25	20.67
2.	Cl	H	H	218	HCl Ethanol/ether	47	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_3\text{S}$	N,	15.35	15.38
3.	H	NO_2	H	182	„ „	55	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{ClN}_4\text{SO}_2$	N,	19.52	19.71
4.	H	H	COOC_2H_5	300	Ethanol	45	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3\text{SO}_2$	N,	15.35	15.27
5.	H	H	COOCH_3	310	„	45	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{SO}_2$	N,	16.17	16.09

* The analytical results are by M/s B. N. Anand and L. K. Khullar of Chemistry Department, Panjab University, Chandigarh.

TABLE II

Sl. No.	Product formed			m.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analytical results		
	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃				Found %	Reqd. %	
1.	H	NO ₂	CH ₃	245	70	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₄ SO ₂	N,	16.20	16.47
2.	NO ₂	NO ₂	CH ₃	255	75	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₅ SO ₄	S,	9.20	9.01
3.	Br	Br	Br	299-300	65	C ₁₄ H ₆ Br ₃ N ₃ S	N,	8.20	8.60
4.	CH ₃	H	H	240	62	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ S	N,	16.14	15.84
5.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	220	60	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ S	N,	15.05	15.07
6.	CH ₃	H	OCH ₃	220	58	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ SO	S,	10.39	10.84
7.	NO ₂	NO ₂	Cl	275	70	C ₁₄ H ₆ ClN ₅ O ₄ S	S,	8.20	8.53
8.	NO ₂	NO ₂	COOH	320	75	C ₁₅ H ₇ N ₆ OO ₈	S,	7.90	8.31
9.	CH ₃	H	COOH	320	60	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ SO ₂	N,	13.88	13.58
10.	CH ₃	H	Cl	250	60	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ S	N,	14.45	14.04
11.	CH ₃	H	OC ₂ H ₅	320	58	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ OS	S,	9.99	10.35
12.	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	210	55	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ S	C,	68.41	68.81
							H,	4.40	4.65
							N,	15.20	15.05
13.	H	NO ₂	COOH	280	70	C ₁₅ H ₈ N ₄ O ₄ S	N,	16.50	16.46

All the compounds were crystallised from acetic acid except No. 3 which was crystallised from ethanol.

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